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perceptions of stakeholders and guardians. A checklist (n=12) captured the general infrastructure of the GWS (e.g., latrines, water and handwashing facilities, cooking and sleeping areas). Key Informant Interviews were conducted with caretakers, hospital staff and Hospital Advisory Committee members (n=28). In-depth Interviews (n=72) and Focus Group Discussions (n=23) with guardians, explored issues of management, access and use of infrastructure and associated behaviours, plus general life at the GWS. Qualitative and quantitative methods were used to analyse the data.

Results:

GWS supported on average 100 patient guardians per day, the majority of whom were predominantly female. Of the 12 GWS assessed, four also served as maternity waiting shelters and four charged user fees for guardians to buy cleaning and lighting materials. Stakeholders described perspectives on who owns and manages GWS. Guardians assumed that GWS belonged to the health care facilities they served, while hospital management typically viewed the GWS as a district or community service that should be managed by those stakeholders. In the absence of clear management and ownership, environmental conditions at GWS were poor. Guardians complained of congested sleeping rooms, lack of electricity, and no facilities to store belongings. Guardians reported intermittent and sporadic access to water (n=5), which limited guardians ability to cook and care for their own hygiene. Nine of the GWS had unusable and or unhygienic toilets which were either full or contained exposed faeces, disregarded used nappies and menstrual hygiene materials. Guardians alternatively used hospital ward latrines, bathing shelters as toilets or openly defecated. Handwashing facilities were only observed in privately owned GWS (n=2) and soap was unavailable. Consequently, GWS users feel their safety and well-being were compromised and were at risk of disease transmission when staying within GWS, such as cholera and COVID.

Conclusion:

GWS are an essential yet much-neglected component of the health service system in Malawi and a much-needed resource for those who attend to their relatives in the hospital. However, their place in the local government systems for management and maintenance is currently unclear, and this has led to long-term neglect. Thus, a coherent and accountable structure is important, which will provide the necessary infrastructure to ensure access and use of GWS is a safe, healthy and dignified environment for guardians and their families.

Household and community risks from informal industrialized bat guano farming facilities in Cambodia

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Introduction:

The STOP Spillover project is a multi-country consortium of partners funded by USAID to identify emerging infectious disease risks, and then design interventions to mitigate and prevent spillover. In Cambodia, the consortium has identified informal industrialized bat guano farming in households as high risk of spillover.

Methods:

To characterize household and community risk for informal industrialized bat guano farming, two concurrent studies were conducted in April 2023: bat ecology; and, food, water, and surfaces. In the bat ecology study, bat guano farming households were visited and completed a survey on: artificial bat roost construction, installation, and maintenance; guano collection practices; knowledge of bats; PPE practices; and, economics of guano sale. Surveillance equipment was left overnight to capture dusk and dawn movements to estimate bat population size; at dawn samples of bat guano and urine were collected and stored in RNAShield. In the food, water, and surfaces study, bat guano farming households and non-bat guano neighbor households were visited. Surveys on demographics, water practices, food practices, hygiene practices, and bat exposures were conducted. Swab samples were collected from high-touch household areas and from food stored uncovered, and stored in RNAShield; drinking water and vegetable gardening water samples were also collected. Tufts and Cambodian institutional review boards approved

both studies, and all samples were stored on ice and transported to the laboratory in Phnom Penh within 12 hours of collection. Samples are currently stored at -80C, with PCR and sequencing for bat DNA (as a surrogate for contamination) and alpha- and beta-coronaviruses (as priority pathogen sampling) pending.

Results:

In April 2023, 14 farming households were enrolled in the bat ecology study, with all completing surveys and 11 completing surveillance; in total 178 samples were collected. Additionally, 10 bat-guano farming and 10 non-bat guano neighbor households were visited; all completed the survey, with 77 water samples and 408 surface and food samples collected. Preliminary analysis indicates that households invest relatively large sums (thousands of USD) in constructing large artificial bat roosts on their property that return a large value to the household (30 USD per bag of guano). Household members have good knowledge of bats, and women are primarily responsible for collecting guano, often with inadequate PPE. Bat guano was visibly present on food and surfaces of both farming and neighbor households. Of note is neighbor households had strikingly lower SES than farming households. Data analysis is currently ongoing, and laboratory results will be available June 2023. Subsequent analysis triangulating survey and laboratory results will identify hotspots of risk for development of targeting mitigation measures.

Discussion:

Informal industrialized bat guano farming in Cambodian households is a highly lucrative business that leads to spillover risk to farmers, farming households, and the surrounding community. These risks may be disproportionately born. Community and household hygiene interventions are needed to reduce spillover risks. Full results from these studies, with recommended interventions to reduce risk, will be fully available by October 2023.

Sanitary inspection characteristics, precipitation, and microbial water quality - A three-country study of rural boreholes in Sub-Saharan Africa

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Sanitary Inspection (SI) is a low-cost on-site risk assessment tool for water supply systems that evaluates conditions, sources of fecal contamination, and common practices that may impact microbial water safety. Research suggests that these scores estimate the vulnerability of water systems to contamination that may be transported or exacerbated by rainfall events. Our research characterizes associations between microbial water safety in boreholes and sanitary inspection data when rainfall and other data are incorporated. This work also characterizes the relative importance of common sanitary inspection items in the case study context.

Data analysis was performed using SI data and microbial water safety (*E. coli* CFU (colony forming unit)/100 mL) data collected from 1200 rural boreholes in Ethiopia, Ghana and Burkina Faso. Composite SI risk scores were calculated for overall sanitary risks as well as for sub-categories (source, transport, and barrier) risks as previously described by Kelly et al. Daily rainfall data were extracted from the Climate Hazards Center InfraRed Precipitation with Station (CHIRPS) dataset. Associations between microbial water quality and either composite or disaggregated sanitary risk scores were evaluated using binary logistic regression (*E. coli* MPN [most probable number] detection/non-detection) and ordered logistic regression (WHO microbial risk category).

Ordered logistic regression indicated that sanitary risk is significantly associated with WHO ordered risk category for microbial contamination when accounting for rainfall, with an odds ratio of 4.15 (95% CI:1.2-13.6). When risk categories were disaggregated, only barrier risk had a significant association with microbial contamination when accounting for rainfall (OR 2.49 [95% CI:1.11- 5.56]) for barrier risk. Binary logistic regression results were qualitatively similar. Seven individual sanitary inspection questions were significant in our analyses: Sewer within 10 meters from water source; cracked/broken drainage channel; stagnant water at/around drainage channel; fencing around water source; presence of cement floor/slab protecting water source; visible cracks in cement floor/slab; presence of wall around cement floor/slab